

**THE DIGITAL
MUSEUM
SERVICES: A
GUIDE FOR
MUSEUMS**

ELISA PELLEGRINI

2020 REPORT

Based on the Network of European Museum Organizations (NEMO) report of increased online traffic during the lockdown of March and April, it was expected that more people visited museums online. Unfortunately, this does not appear to be the case. During the same months, I asked 225 Italian residents why they visited (online) museums and, in this paper, the main results are summarized, combined with what has been discovered and described by the International Council of Museums (ICOM Italy) in its document "Words of digital communication. Small practical advices for museums". The aim of this report is thus to explain how museums could fully explore and exploit the digital opportunities available.

CONTEXT

For many years, museums have been developing online services as virtual tours, they have made collection databases available on their websites, and they have started to publish digital content on social media. However, these online services have become of greater significance in Italy as governments closed institutions the **8th of March** till the **end of May**, as part of the **health measures** to **prevent** further spread of the **COVID-19 outbreak**. The **lockdown** prevented individuals to physically visit museums as everybody was practicing **social distance** and was **quarantined** at home.

After a brief period in which museums reopened, but with many restrictions, they have been closed again, from **November 3rd** until **December 3rd**. From June to early November, most of these cultural institutions were only open on weekends

and it was always necessary to book the visit in advance. These measures are part of a **new normality**, whose aim is to find a balance between the need of ensuring social distance between visitors and the re-opening of museums.

CLOSING
OF
MUSEUMS

LIMITED
RESOURCES

UNCERTAINTY

AUDIENCE
PERSPECTIVE

In this context, **technology** has become an extremely valuable tool that enables museums to continue to deliver arts and culture to their audience.

Art museums have quickly developed **innovative strategies**, often using digital technologies, to continue delivering arts and culture to their audience and thus to pursue their mission of exhibiting cultural heritage “*for the purposes of education, study and enjoyment*” (ICOM, 2007). However, investing in the creation of new products and services requires the allocation of **resources** particularly **limited** at this time, as museums **miss** the **income** generated from **ticket sales** (NEMO, 2020).

In addition, the **unprecedented nature** of the current situation provides **little**

comparison for museums to understand what consumers want, need, or prefer as digital services have remained rather marginal in many museums. Therefore, understanding the **perspective of the audience**, comprehending visitors’ values toward the services art museums are implementing, if visitors find those services interesting and how they would better them is crucial. In order to investigate these topics, it is necessary to focus on the **demand side**, considering its **expectations** and the possible **barriers** that prevent consumers to use the digital services offered by museums. In addition, it is also crucial to understand if the **investments** made are in the right direction, being able to satisfy customers’ needs. In fact, many museums are short of resources and complex projects require larger

investments. Consequently, a **guide** of what people want may be useful to museums in future allocation of resources.

In order to investigate the above, during the months of **March** and **April**, I conducted a **research** on which online services were provided by museums, focusing my attention on the **audience point of view**.

The study have demonstrated that even if online consumption was the only option available to visit museums, the percentage of **non-visitors** has only slightly decreased (**from 47,6% to 42,7%**). Overall, the **demographic** and **socioeconomic** characteristics of the audience are the same as before, indicating that it is difficult to attract new visitors: to appreciate online museums services or to just consume cultural products and services, consumers need **social and cultural capital** and **previous experience**.

Therefore, once the perspective of customers in relation to online content delivered by museums has been analyzed, **cultural institutions** and **policymakers** need to understand how to attract the non-visitors.

Museums have the tools to take initiative in developing further the services already present in the market, in **creating** new customer propositions and in undertaking decisions that can **facilitate** a greater consumption of culture online. Therefore, the digital tools that cultural organizations have been implementing in the last months are a way to act but services can be **improved** to best respond to the *new normal*. As a consequence of that, the aim of this paper is to point **what actions museums could implement to attract the non-visitors and to continue to attract their customers**.

SLIGHTLY DECREASE OF THE PERCENTAGE OF NON-VISITORS (FROM 47,6% TO 42,7%)

DIFFICULTY IN ATTRACTING NEW VISITORS: IMPORTANCE OF THE SOCIAL AND CULTURAL CAPITAL AND PREVIOUS EXPERIENCE

CONSISTENCY OF THE DEMOGRAPHIC AND SOCIOECONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS OF THE AUDIENCE

ROLE OF MUSEUMS AND POLICYMAKERS IN ATTRACTING THE NON-VISITORS

DIGITAL SERVICES

A museum is a “*permanent institution in the service of society and its development, open to the public, which acquires, conserves, researches, communicates and exhibits the tangible and intangible heritage of humanity and its environment*” (ICOM, 2007). All these activities of acquisition, preservation, research, communication, collection and education are identifiable in the online services that museums are currently providing according to the Network of European Museum Organizations (NEMO, 2020):

- Online learning programs
- Online exhibitions
- Virtual Tours
- Podcast
- YouTube programs
- Newsletter
- Live content (as live museums tour)
- Online collection
- Social media
- Quizzes and contests

This paper refers in particular to free services delivered by museums as leisure activities, both in an entertainment and educative sense. Therefore, the focus is on the following online offers:

POPULATION

The study has been developed during the months of March and April, looking at **225 consumers in Italy**, delivering **self-**

completion questionnaires to **potential visitors of art museums** (Table 1).

Table 1. Overview of the population investigated

		Percent
Gender	Female	70,2
	Male	29,8
Total		100,0
Age	18-24	28,4
	25-34	24,4
	35-44	15,6
	45-54	8,0
	55-64	20,4
	65+	3,1
Total		100,0
Profession/ Area of study	Clerks	9,8
	Elementary occupations	0,9
	Legislators, senior officials and managers	30,7
	Physicals, mathematicians, engineers, health professionals	20,4
	Teachers, other professionals (social science, creative art, architecture, journalism)	29,8
	Other	8,4
Total		100,0
Education	Basic education	2,2
	Intermediate education	26,2
	Tertiary education	71,6
Total		100,0

STRATEGY

The focus in this paper is on the actions that museums could take in order to fully explore and exploit the digital opportunities. In particular, it is possible to delineate six different fields of action on which museums could focus on:

In order to achieve an ideal result, also the synergetic actions of policymakers would be necessary. Policymakers could create the suitable context for the consumption of digital museums services by developing strategies to decrease the **digital divide** in Italy and to increase the level of **digital literacy** of the Italian population. In fact, according to the 2018 edition of the **Measuring the Information Society Report**, compiled by **ITU**, which is the United Nations specialized agency for information and communication technologies that provides information of the status of the ICT markets in 192 countries, the level of digital literacy of Italy is lower in respect to the rest of Europe. The percentage of individuals using the Internet in Italy (61.3%) is lower than in Europe (77.2%), as well as the percentage of households with a computer (64.3% in Italy and 78.6% in Europe), and the percentage of households with Internet access (71.7% in Italy and 80.6% in Europe) (ITU, 2018) (Table 2).

Table 2. Measuring the Information Society Report (ITU, 2018).

Key Indicators for Italy (2017)	Italy	Europe	World
Mobile-cellular sub. per 100 inhab.	141.3	120.4	103.6
Active mobile-broadband sub. per 100 inhab.	87.9	85.9	61.9
3G coverage (% of population)	100.0	98.3	87.9
Individuals using the Internet (%)	61.3	77.2	48.6
Households with a computer (%)	64.3	78.6	47.1
Households with Internet access (%)	71.7	80.6	54.7
International bandwidth per Internet user (kbit/s)	35.7	117.5	76.6
Fixed-broadband sub. per 100 inhab.	27.9	30.4	13.6

RESEARCH

Museums could benefit from developing a similar research to the one I conducted, but directing it towards their audience, in order to implement their services taking into account the specific needs of their mission and public. This kind of study could be done digitally, through the museum newsletter, or physically, distributing surveys to the visitors of the museum.

In case the museum's resources are not sufficient to support this type of research, it is always possible to be updated on the subject reading the reports written by institutions such as the Network of European Museum Organization (NEMO) or the International Council of Museums (ICOM).

NETWORK OF EUROPEAN MUSEUM ORGANIZATION

- NEMO is currently publishing a follow-up survey after its first research in May 2020 on the impact of COVID-19 on museums.
- This survey will be an in-depth assessment of income losses, its consequences and mitigation; the development of digital museum offer; and questions related to a "new normal", including the re-assessment of museum's priorities and success criteria.
- The survey is directed to people who work in museums and the answers are accepted until Friday 20 November 2020. By participating in the survey, NEMO will be able to determine which policies and measures to propose at European level.

INTERNATIONAL COUNCIL OF MUSEUMS

- Between 23 and 30 April 2020, ICOM Italy conducted a survey on what museums have achieved in terms of digital communication since their closure. In total, responses were obtained from 354 different museums.
- Part of the results obtained from this research are summarized in this report.

COMMUNICATION

30.06% of respondents confirmed that before museums closed due to COVID-19, they did not consume the online services provided by museums because they did not know they existed. Despite this, the research results demonstrate the existence of a demand for digital cultural products (Table 3). Therefore, improving the communication of the products and services offered by museums is crucial in order to make known what is offered and to facilitate the consumer access to these products.

Table 3. Comparison of online visits of museums before museums were closed and after their closing.

	Frequency of viewing contents of museums online before Italy closed museums	Frequency of viewing contents of museums online after Italy closed museums
	Percent	Percent
Everyday	0,4	2,7
Several times a week	5,3	11,1
Once a week	4,0	11,1
1-3 times a month	12,0	12,9
Less often	30,7	19,6
Never	47,6	42,7
Total	100,0	100,0

According to the research conducted by ICOM Italy (2020), **more than a third** of the museums analyzed, during the closing period, did not report on the site an explicit reference to the many activities carried out on social channels (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Reference website - social channels

Uffizi Decameron in rete!

Le Gallerie aprono la loro pagina Facebook
[The Gallerie open their Facebook page](#)

A **correct and constant reference** between the website and the social channels is crucial. If museums are still closed, it can be helpful to make sure that on their website there is a clear reference to their social channels, not only as icons, but with an **ad hoc communication** (eg. a **news**). This also applies if museums have verified that social channels are a direct access point for many. In case museums reopen, they could benefit from making sure that on their website the references to their social channels are always clear and that, conversely, the reference to the website is clearly present on the socials. Applying these strategies means **making easier** for the public to follow the digital initiatives of museums (ICOM, 2020).

Finally, only **27%** of the museums analyzed published content relating to the objects in **storage**. **Rethinking the communication** of it

can **create curiosity and attention** both for digital users, who for various reasons cannot visit the museum, and for users who are now digital and tomorrow physical. **Feedback** from the web and social media can inspire new curatorial choices (ICOM, 2020).

VISITORS

As observed by the art historian Mottola Molfino in her text "*Theoretical and practical reflections (and some advice) for museums at the time of Covid-19*" (2020), the first imperative is to not abandon old aficionados and possible future visitors, creating for them multiple opportunities, also personalized, of virtual meeting.

The virtual activities do not have to be just of teaching or entertainment but they aim to build a **strong supportive community** with their virtual visitors. In fact, keeping enthusiasts, friends and stakeholders connected to the museum is the first aim of this virtual activity that was immediately offered by museums for free. The **dialogue** must be **intense** and **highly personalized** because the **loyalty** and the **participation** of this public will also be precious for future starts. Museum associates must be offered many opportunities to feel part of the museum as well as integrated in the staff.

For example, asking them for **suggestions, proposals, solidarity** and even **material help and donations**. One way could be to **explore the collections together**, dedicating all the possible energies of the conservators and registrars to reorder **inventories**, to develop specific studies on single objects and collections, to arrange the **deposits**, to carry out **maintenance and restorations**. In short, to **show** everyone the museum **behind the scenes** while preparing for the reopening (Mottola Molfino, 2020).

CONTENTS

The results of the questionnaire highlight the importance of differentiating the public of a museum, taking into account the specific needs of different age groups.

As visible from the trend lines in Figure 5, the **youngest** segment of the population (18-35 years old) prefers services that are **interactive**, while the **oldest** segment (35-65+) has a strong preference for **education**. The population investigated respects the findings of previous research, that stress

the importance of both **individualistic values**, such as **education and knowledge**, both **socially oriented values**, related to spend time with family and friends and to share the experience with them through **interactive activities** such as games, quizzes and contests research.

Figure 5. Types of services preferred by respondents who have not consumed museums online services in the last months and knew about them, according to their age.

MEDIUM

Analyzing what the population investigated generally looks for when consuming the content of museums online and the evaluations given by the audience about the services offered, it is possible to understand what are the tools that if developed and implemented would bring benefits to museums.

Activities related to the **acquisition of information** and the **desire to learn new notions** present the highest index. In fact, the reasons “learn something new” and “learn directly from the experts of the field” respectively score 1 and 0.87 (Table 6). These results are aligned with what previous research have demonstrated, according to which visitors of online contents of museums are moved by a **personal interest** in the subject covered by an exhibition displayed and the desire to **find information** in order to learn

something new. In addition, also the reasons “look at art” and “visit a museum that I have never had the chance to visit before” are considered extremely important. These motivations are aligned with the preferences demonstrated by the respondents for the online services as **virtual tours, online collection** and **online exhibitions** (Table 7). However, overall all the services provided show rather high scores and, in particular, **social media, live contents** and **YouTube videos** present a result close to 1.

Table 6. Reasons to watch the content of museums online.

	Index
Learn something new	1.00
Look at art	0.97
Visit a museum that I have never had the chance to visit before	0.92
Learn directly from the experts of the field (e.g. online exhibition explained by its curator)	0.87
Have access to high quality pictures of artworks	0.83
Relaxing activity	0.80
Be creatively inspired	0.79
Be updated with the news of a specific museum	0.67
Test my knowledge on art history (e.g. test and quizzes)	0.62
Conclude the physical visit of a museum I have already been to with the online experience	0.59

Table 7. Evaluation of the online services provided.

	Index
Virtual tours	1.00
Live contents (e.g. live museum tour, Instagram stories)	0.92
Social media	0.91
Online collection	0.90
Online exhibitions	0.90
YouTube	0.89
Online learning programs (quizzes and contests)	0.80
Podcast	0.70

The population investigated in my survey respects the trend showed in the data of NEMO document, that means a **great interest in social media, videos, virtual tours, online collections and online exhibitions**. After 3 weeks in which they were closed to the public because of social distancing, museums have increased their digital services in order to reach their audience (NEMO, 2020). According to the ICOM report (2020), about the **70%** of the museums activated new social channels or reactivated **social channels** which had remained completely or mostly unused (Figure 8).

- **44%** opened a **YouTube channel**;

Figure 8. Have you activated new social channels (or reactivated silent channels) after closing?

- **27%** opened an **Instagram** account,
- **10%** opened a **Facebook** page,
- **8%** activated an account on platforms where they could upload **podcasts** (Spotify, Spreaker, etc.)
- **6%** activated **Twitter** (Figure 9).

Social media have been the digital service **more developed** during these months. In fact, due to the **budget restrictions** of the last period, museums have especially developed online services that did not require extra investments, time, costs and skills. Therefore, services as podcasts, live content and online learning have not been the priority (NEMO, 2020).

Figure 9. New channels activated.

Therefore, the majority of museums focused on **YouTube**. However, it is found that the activation of a new channel does not often correspond to a precise **editorial choice** and in several cases the idea of a **publication calendar** (content distributed over time) seems to be completely **lacking** (ICOM, 2020).

An analysis of the YouTube channels opened by the museum institutions during the period of forced lockdown shows that, in preparation for the launch of the new medium, a certain amount of video content

was produced. Even if the attempt was to follow some editorial lines (for example with the creation of columns or thematic strands), the contents were uploaded massively in a very short period of time. This has meant that, in many cases, it has **not** been possible to **gradually capitalize** the interest of the public and the channel has thus **not grown organically** (ICOM, 2020).

As a consequence of these observations, ICOM Italy has delineated some **suggestions** (Box 1 e 2).

Box 1. Guidelines (ICOM, 2020).

DOSING THE PUBLICATIONS

Having content ready does not mean publishing it all at the same time.

VIRTUOUS CYCLE

Opening a new channel means supporting it and making it known through the other digital channels of the institution.

CALL TO ACTION

Opening a new YouTube channel means inviting the contacts of the museum to follow the channel. In fact, if the user goes to other platforms regardless, it is essential for YouTube that the user is informed of the presence of its new content and this happens automatically if he is subscribed to the channel.

The greater availability of time by the human resources of the institution during the period of forced lockdown has meant that the **internal production of videos** has **increased exponentially**. The new channels, as well as the silent ones recovered in recent months, have therefore found themselves to be populated by a **large amount of content** in a very short time (ICOM, 2020).

If in the months of **April and May more videos were published per day**, since **mid-May**, in most cases, the **frequency** has been **greatly reduced**, leaving the user with the impression that the channel was particularly active in the period of closing, but will soon return into the **oblivion** (ICOM, 2020).

Box 2. Guidelines (ICOM, 2020).

**GIVE
CONTINUITY**

Regardless of what has been done during the closing period, it is essential not to let the editorial lines started to die, even if the frequency of publication will inevitably be reduced.

**RESUME
CONTENTS**

Having already posted contents on YouTube does not mean they cannot have a new life. An idea could be remember through the other social channels and/or in newsletters that it is possible to access the contents produced in the past months.

**MONITORING
AND NEW
CONTENT**

Analyze the contents that have had a greater and better response and invest the current resources to continue the activity in that direction.

MONITORING

A museum that aims at controlling the progress of the contents it publishes could benefit by developing continuous monitoring actions of its social channels and its website.

According to the survey implemented by ICOM Italy, **more than the 80%** of the museums that have completed the questionnaire responded positively to the question regarding the **monitoring** of their digital campaigns/activities (Figure 10).

Subsequently, to the museums who answered “Yes” to the question “Are you monitoring the results of your digital campaigns/activities?” the further question “Please indicate, if available, the first results/trends” was submitted (Figure 11).

- **46%** of the museums made **very general declarations** (e.g. positive trend, we are satisfied, etc.);
- **20%** of museums declared that they have **no data available**;
- **2,5%** of the museums stated that the **data are in elaboration**;
- **27%** of the museums reported **more detailed data**;
- **4,5%** of the museums gave **other types of answers** (e.g. the role of the compiler does not guarantee access to the data).

Figure 10. Are you monitoring the results of your campaigns/digital activities?

Figure 11. Please indicate, if available, the first results/trends.

The fact that 20% of the museums said they had no data available rings an **alarm bell**, as **monitoring** is something that should be **constantly done** and, although resources are limited, "not having data available" is inconsistent with the "Yes" answer to the question "are you monitoring" (ICOM, 2020). In addition, the remaining 46% of the museums made very general statements. Net of the assessment that some museums may have deliberately decided not to share more precise data (for privacy, lack of time during compilation, etc.), it remains the **doubt** that the institution does not have data available and

therefore monitoring is superficial (ICOM, 2020).

It follows the Table 12 in which examples of monitoring actions of the social networks and the website are described (ICOM, 2020).

- With **15 minutes a day** it is possible to carry out **basic monitoring** of Facebook, Instagram and the website.
- With **45 minutes a week** it is possible to carry out a **in-depth monitoring** of Facebook, Instagram and the website.

Table 12. Monitoring of Facebook, Instagram and the website (ICOM, 2020).

	 WEBSITE		
WHEN?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Take a look at the Insights (every day). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Take a look at the Insights (every day). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Take a look at the Analytics (every day).
WHAT TO WATCH?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The summary page (5 minutes); • Look at the detail pages (at least once a week, 10 to 20 minutes); • Analysis of peak moments and related content. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The summary page (5 minutes); • Posts, stories or specific promotions, to check their (2 minutes if done daily). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The summary page (5 minutes); • Look at the detail pages (at least once a week, 10 to 20 minutes).
WHAT TO DO?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify strengths and weaknesses of the editorial plan and modify it accordingly. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify strengths and weaknesses of the editorial plan and modify it accordingly. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify strengths and weaknesses of the editorial plan and modify it accordingly.

CONCLUSIONS

As summarized in this report, museums could benefit from applying all or some of the six strategies mentioned.

- **RESEARCH:** interviewing your audience, as well as looking at the reports edited by other institutions and organizations is crucial to know and thus satisfy the demand;
- **COMMUNICATION:** people are often unaware that various digital products and services exist and they are available for free. Improving the communication of these services would facilitate their access to consumers;
- **VISITORS:** creating a community and working on loyalty and public participation is crucial to keep enthusiasts and stakeholders connected to the institution;
- **CONTENTS:** the content of digital services offered by museums must be differentiated according to the specific characteristics of the public. Different age groups have different needs and thus different expectations;

- **MEDIUM:** analyzing what the investigated population generally looks for when consuming the contents of online museums and the evaluations of the public on the online services offered, it is possible to understand which are the tools that if developed and implemented would bring benefits to museums;
- **MONITORING:** a museum that aims at controlling the progress of the contents it publishes could benefit by developing continuous monitoring actions of its social channels and its website.

Implementing the actions described means preparing to face a *new normal*, continuing to attract the public that already visits the museums and attracting those who currently are non-visitors. However, as previously explained in the report, synergistic action with policy makers would be essential for an optimal result.

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